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Gren' Larisa Nikolaevna

PhD in pedagogy, Associate Professor of the Department of pedagogy and psychology of social systems management, National technical university “Kharkiv Polytechnic Institute” (NTU “KhPI”); Kharkiv, Ukraine

ORCID ID: 0000-0003-4466-6018

Karlyuk Sergei Vladimirovich

Senior lecturer at the Department of business foreign languages and translation, V.N. Karazin National University; Kharkiv, Ukraine

The role of vocational education in the context of ensuring the national security of Ukraine

The article discloses the functions of vocation-and-technical training in society that influence ensuring of a country's national security; there is proved the need in state management of vocation-and-technical training's development to raise efficiency of its operation in various activity spheres in the interests of national security of Ukraine.

Keywords: *state security, national security of Ukraine, education activities, vocation-and-technical training, functions of vocation-and-technical training.*

One of priorities of national interests of Ukraine is guarantying constitutional rights of a person and a citizen; creating a competitive, a socially oriented market economy; integrating Ukraine into the European political, economic, and legal environment [3]. The Law of Ukraine “On National Security of Ukraine” of 21.06.2018

No.2469-VIII defines the National Security Strategy of Ukraine as “a document that determines actual threats to Ukraine’s national security along with corresponding aims, tasks, and mechanisms of protecting national interests of Ukraine and is a basis for planning and realization of state policies within the sphere of national security” [3].

The National Security of Ukraine Strategy defines general principles, priority goals, tasks, and mechanism of protecting vital interests of a person, society, and the state from external threats.

The issues of national security of Ukraine are always within the circle of scientific interest of many authors. Worth mentioning are scientific works by Yu. Nikitin (disclosed problems, risks, and influence factors affecting the national security of Ukraine) [8]; T. Tswigun (researched the place of economic security within the national security of Ukraine; identified main threats to economic security; analyzed the main components of Ukraine’s national security: macroeconomic, production, financial, investment, power-generation, demographic, social, food-supply, scientific; researched the main state policies directions in the sphere of the country’s economic security) [13]; O. Ustimeko (viewed the national security monitoring as one of the elements of the strategic planning mechanism; proved that improvement of the state strategic planning system, creating a unified system of monitoring, analysis, forecasting, and taking decisions in the sphere of national security and defense, ensuring efficient coordination and functioning of the unified system of situational centers of profile state power bodies of the security and defense sector is an important element in the process of forming an efficient security and defense sector) [12], as well as other scientists.

In scientists’ opinion, “the analysis of the notion of ‘national security’ and directions concerning its understanding is determined by the fact that this notion is a foundation in forming the national security concept of any state, which is the prime mover at determining the national security policies, the main function of which is to determine the principal interests of nations and creating guidelines when forming main

strategies concerning the current and future threats, as well as possibilities of eliminating them” [1, p. 42].

As O. Glazov is convinced, the main elements within the national security structure is state security (a notion that characterizes the level of state's being protected from outer and internal threats); civil security (a notion expressed in the level of a personality and society protection from internal threats mainly); technogenic security (protection level from technogenic threats); ecology safety and protection from the threats of natural forces; economic security; energy-generation security; information security; personal security [1, p.43]. In A. Pomaza-Ponomarenko's opinion, “one can relate to the main principles of state management in the sphere of national security provision in the international affairs the following principles: priority of rights and freedoms of a person and a citizen; supremacy of law; priority of agreement-based (peaceful) means of settling conflicts; timeliness and adequacy of measures of national security protection to real and potential threats; a clear delimitation of authority and efficient interaction of state power bodies in ensuring national security; democratic civil control over the security and defenses sector; applying in the interest of Ukraine the international systems and international collective security mechanism” [10, pp. 21 – 22].

As G. Sytnyk correctly points out, “the national security of a state is a category that characterizes the extent (measure, level) of protection of vitally important interests, rights, and freedom of a personality, society, and the state from external and internal threats or the degree of absence of threats to rights and freedoms of a person, to basic interests and values of society and the state [2].

In this research, we will consider the national security as “an ability of a nation to satisfy the needs needed for its self-preservation, self-restoration, and self-improvement with minimum risk of damage to its current basic values” [5, p. 1].

Educative activities and security are closely connected with one another as well as with social, economic, and humanitarian processes and phenomena. Researchers

single out the following threats that have a high probability “of actualizing in the event of procrastination in overcoming negative tendencies in the sphere of education: threat to economic growth and competitiveness; threat to military security; threat to information security; threat to global interests of the country; threat to the nation’s unity and consolidation” [14].

Considerable importance in a country’s national security pertains to education in general, and vocation-and-technical training in particular. Vocation-and-technical education ensures that citizens obtain professions according to their predisposition, interests, skills, as well as pre-professional training, re-training, qualifications improvement [part three of Article 3 in the edition of the Law No. 1158-IV of 11.09.2003]. Education is a priority for a state which ensures innovative, socio-economic, and cultural development of society. The state policies in the sphere of education is determined by the Verkhovna Rada (Supreme Council) of Ukraine, to be carried out by the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine, the central body of executive power in the sphere of science and education, along with other executive power central bodies and local authorities [4].

The documents regulating state prognosticating and strategic planning of education development are Development Prognostication of Ukraine, Development Strategy of Education in Ukraine, corresponding state, regional, and local purpose programs, education activities programs by power bodies (Law of Ukraine “On Education”. Article 5, point 4).

In this research, we deem it necessary to consider efficacy of such priorities of the national security of Ukraine as guaranteeing constitutional rights of education, Ukraine’s integration into the European education environment within the system of vocational (vocation-and-technical) education.

Education is the basis of a personality’s intellectual, spiritual, physical, and cultural development, its successful socializing, and economic well-being, a token of development of a society united by common values and culture, and of state

development as well. The Law of Ukraine “On Education” regulates social relations that arise in the process of realizing a constitutional right on education, rights and duties of physical and juridical persons who participate in realization of this right, and this law also defines the authority of state bodies and local authorities in the sphere of education [4]. The right on education is one of the main inalienable constitutional rights of citizens of Ukraine, but this right can be true, substantial, and real only on condition that a country is under no threat, for violation of security of a state makes its realization impossible. “The state creates conditions for obtaining a civic education aimed at forming competencies related to a person’s exercising their rights and duties as a member of society, realizing the values of civil (free democratic) society, supremacy of law, rights and freedoms of a person and citizen” [4].

From the time of declaration of Ukraine’s independence, vocational (vocation-and-technical) training has been on its own, pertaining to it only, way of development and modernizing, having set the goal of joining the world education environment. The complication of this process is determined by the tendencies and challenges that have formed in the current education system, which “is experiencing a period of radical changes in methods, information contents, and education environment” [15]. Vocation-and technical training in Ukraine is one of inalienable components of the education system of Ukraine. The issue of strategic development of the system of professional employees training, a long-term strategy of human resources development in conditions of innovative economy formation and evolvement of civilized market is the most complicated due to the fact that the success of their solving is determined by synergic impact of a great many of factors. One of the key factors that determine innovative systems’ competitiveness is a highly qualified workforce whose professional activities are directed at ensuring the country’s national security. In general, scientists consider the main indicators of national security as being represented by the following factors: “national independence and sovereignty, territorial integrity of a state; development of civil society, democracy level, completeness and efficiency of

legislative base of a legal state, a person's protection; economic capacity of a state; the state of military force, its ability and readiness for combat; national identity and distinctiveness; development of national self-perception and culture; availability of general strategy of national development, of "national idea", common goal; national consensus and unity; inner political stability, readiness and ability of political forces to actualize common goals" [1, p. 44].

Creation of efficient vocational (vocation-and-technical) training system capable of ensuring the needs in innovative development of a country's economy with necessary personnel is mentioned as one of priority tasks of the Concept of education development.

The Law of Ukraine "On Education" establishes the following levels of vocational (vocation-and-technical) training:

- the vocational (vocation-and-technical) training level wherein a person can obtain qualifications that correspond to the second level of the National Qualifications Frame;

- the second (basic) level of vocational (vocation-and-technical) training wherein a person can obtain qualifications that correspond to the third level of the National Qualifications Frame;

- the third (higher) level of vocational (vocation-and-technical) training wherein a person can obtain qualifications that correspond to the fourth level of the National Qualifications Frame [4].

At every level of vocational (vocation-and-technical) training there takes place realization of the following important both for the state and society functions:

- training function: Reforming of vocational (vocation-and-technical) training in Ukraine is connected with its fundamentalization, flexibility, multi-directedness, and standardizing. A fundamental vocational training will enable to work both in the main profession (specialization) and in information and social sphere, facilitate young

people's employment on completing their training, improve professional mobility, and in case of the next employment it will ensure access to open vacancies [11];

- social security function: In light of democratic transformations, the function of youth's social security is to become priority. This function is realized when young people enter market relationships through obtaining a quality vocation-and-technical training that provides for the graduates an opportunity of being competitive and mobile in the labor market, and, consequently, socially protected [6, p. 17]. The vocational (vocation-and-technical) training system ensures vocational training for orphans, children deprived of parents' care, children with specific education needs, etc., as well as unemployed people;

- economic function: vocational (vocation-and-technical) training system supposes planned restoration of qualified labor resources for all branches of economy. Comparatively brief periods of training and re-training for working professions considering an ever-growing demand for them, makes the vocational (vocation-and-technical) training system one of the most important state policy factors of influencing population's employment. Due to revival of the economy of Ukraine, about 60% of vacancies in the labor market are currently vacancies in working professions;

- education function: upbringing of personal responsibility in every trainee for their actions in future professional activities; educating of a highmoral standards personality, a conscientious citizen; a person who obeys and respects laws of the country will keep state secret in any circumstances, will promote ensuring national security of Ukraine.

The goal of the Concept of vocation-and-technical training development for 2010 – 2020 [7] is raising the education to an utterly new level, enhancing further evolvement of vocation-and-technical training in Ukraine. In I. Musiyenko's opinion, "to accomplish the ideas of national interests' realization, it is necessary to bring the education system at a completely new level, because it is education which is the foundation of knowledge and intellectual capital formation" and further on, "ensuring

of educational policies at due level is a guarantee of Ukraine's independence, as well as stable development and growth of people's well-being" [9, p.1]. For realization of this goal, qualitatively new changes are taking place in vocation-and-technical training of Ukraine. The Ministry of science and education of Ukraine is planning to bring for consideration of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine meeting the Concept of reform in vocational training along with the Draft law "On Vocational Training". According to the minister of science and education of Ukraine, "the reform in vocational training will be accompanied with not only a large-scale infrastructure modernization, but also with changes in standards, as well as re-training teachers and trainers working in vocational training". Within the third component of the Draft law, it is planned to continue the work started by the government on renovating the materiel and technical base of vocational training institutions, particularly through forming the network of Professional Improvement Centers. The Draft law supposes formation of 7 multifunction multi-profiled centers. Sums will be allocated on reconstruction or building facilities, purchasing instruments and equipment, and so on.

The main values of vocational training systems are: restoration and growth of intellectual, spiritual, and economic potential of society; creating conditions for personality development and creative self-realization of each citizen of Ukraine; educating a generation of people capable of working and studying efficiently for life; preserving and multiplying the values of national culture and civil society; development and strengthening the sovereign, independent, democratic, social, and legal state as an inalienable part of the European and the world community. The basic values of vocational (vocation-and-technical) training system have an immediate impact on ensuring and strengthening the national security of a state. The rating estimation of vocation-and-technical training institutions' activities enables to determine the tendencies in the development of vocational (vocation-and-technical) training, to improve, and to develop them on the basis of analyzing its quantitative and qualitative indicators. The system approach to rating estimation of education quality,

particularly of vocation-and-technical institutions' activities at all levels of vocational (vocation-and-technical) training management within the context of regional and industrial needs of production and services will ensure the correspondence of vocational training and teaching to the requirements of the state, society, and personality; raise its productivity, and enable to control efficiently the processes of vocational (vocation-and-technical) training system's development, improving thus the national security of Ukraine.

Education system, caring of students' safety, is called to solve the issue of providing for every person the knowledge, skills, and abilities needed for ensuring one's personal safety, forming the safety culture in the process of training. Thus, at general secondary education establishments, pupils study the courses in "Basics of safe life activities", at vocation-and-technical training establishments they have "Life activities safety", at higher education establishments they have courses like "Social and psychological safety", etc. While learning these courses, the trainees get accustomed to act in a responsible and correct way, taking into accounts community's interests.

The task of vocational (vocation-and-technical) training system in solving the national security issues is also training professionals who in their perspective work will detect and follow one or other kinds of threats, develop measures to prevent them, or to neutralize dangerous situations. That is why Ukraine has specialized education establishments that conduct training specialists for environmental, rescuing, military, law enforcement, and other services.

One of important tasks within the context of national security is also training and re-training personnel in organizing security systems. In every oblast of the country, there work training-and-methodological centers of civil defense and life activities safety, operation of which is connected with organizing and realizing fulfilment of measures in the matters of civil defense, providing other education services and methodological support of economy subjects. They conduct training of the population to act in extraordinary situations, accidents, and terroristic attacks.

Considering the aforementioned, we can outline the following conclusions. First, education, and vocation-and-technical training in particular, should become the basis of national security of the state. Secondly, taking into account the contents of the vocation-and-technical training's functions (training, social, economic, educative), and correspondently those of state bodies, we can state that vocation-and-technical training plays an important role in ensuring national security of Ukraine.

In our opinion, the influence of integration processes on professional safety is a perspective direction in this problematics.

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